

Governance Barriers to WASH Service Delivery in Sub-Saharan Africa: A Systematic Review

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Abstract: In Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), governance structures and enabling environment plays a significant role in ensuring effective WASH services, yet challenges persist in policy and legislative implementation, regulatory frameworks and institutional coordination. This systematic review seeks to critically examine governance barriers that hinder effective WASH service delivery across SSA region. This study adopts the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta Analyses (PRISMA) methodology to identify, select, and analyze relevant studies that explore policy, institutional, legislative and regulatory constraints to WASH implementation in sub-Saharan Africa. The findings reveal that barriers to WASH services in SSA are deeply entrenched in weak governance structures, fragmented institutional mandates, poor financing mechanisms, and inadequate regulations.

Keywords: WASH, Water Governance, Sanitation Governance, Policy, legislation and institutions, regulations, Sub-Saharan Africa.

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1.0 Introduction

Water, Sanitation, and Hygiene (WASH) services are foundational to human health, dignity, and sustainable development. Yet, across Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA), millions continue to lack access to safe drinking water, basic sanitation, and hygienic conditions, posing severe risks to public health, education, livelihoods, and gender equity. According to Kanyangarara et al., (2021), 400 million people in the region still lack access to basic drinking water (WHO/UNICEF 2023) and nearly 800 million lack basic sanitation. These deficits undermine the attainment of Sustainable Development Goal 6 (SDG 6), which aims to “ensure availability and sustainable management of water and sanitation for all” by 2030.

At the heart of these challenges lies a critical but often underemphasized factor which is WASH governance (Cookey et al. 2017, Bayu et al. 2020). The Social and Political dimensions of Water Governance are key in influencing the occurrence of inequality of access to sanitation services. The key barriers to WASH services delivery included the political economy of decision making (Sinharoy et al. 2019). Governance is defined as the tradition and institutions by which authority in a country is exercised, including the processes by which governments are selected, monitored and replaced; the capacity of government to effectively formulate, and implement sound policies' the respect of citizens and the state for the institutions that govern economic and social interactions" (Kaufmann 2011). It can also be viewed as the process through which institutions, policies and norms are managed, and decisions are made and implemented, including how citizens participate and hold decision makers account, in addition to the exercise of economic, political, and administrative authority to manage a country's affairs at all levels plays a pivotal role in shaping the planning, delivery, regulation, and monitoring of WASH services (UNDP 2021). Effective WASH governance encompasses policy coherence, institutional clarity, stakeholder participation, transparency, and accountability mechanisms. Without these core attributes, efforts to expand WASH access tend to be fragmented, donor-dependent, inequitable, and unsustainable (UNDP 2021).

In recent years, the role of governance in accelerating SDG 6 has gained prominence in global WASH discourse. Well-functioning governance systems can facilitate the integration of WASH into national development plans, enhance coordination across ministries and agencies, mobilize domestic and external financing, and ensure that services are delivered equitably and inclusively. Jimenez et al. (2024) argues that institutional arrangements' performance is one of the identified bottlenecks for successful water governance, they are crucial for reliable and affordable WASH services and accountability. This cross-sector alignment can also foster bottom-top accountability by involving communities in decision-making, particularly marginalized groups such as women, youth, and persons with disabilities. The African Ministers' Council on Water (AMCOW) and the Sanitation and Water for All (SWA) Partnership have emphasized governance as a "missing link" in the drive toward universal WASH access (Valcourt et al 2020).

Over the past decade, an increasing number of studies have provided empirical and theoretical insights into how governance structures significantly shape the trajectory of WASH service delivery and the realization of Sustainable Development Goal 6 (SDG 6). Momberg et al (2021) links WASH outcomes to governance arrangements and highlights governance as a mediator of service access and child nutrition, "WASH and Governance are linked; Governance factors influence access to services and child nutritional outcomes" Furthermore Valcourt et al. (2020) posits that system level governance (Institutions, Coordination, roles) is central to sustainable WASH service delivery; adding that siloed governance undermines sustainability, "Systems approaches reveal governance gaps-fragmentation and unclear roles undermines sustainable WASH services". While Yasmin et al. (2023) argues that institutional capacity and multi-level coordination are decisive for WASH resilience and sustainability. Some other authors aligned to these as well such as Evaristo et al. (2023) "As 2030 nears, reimagining water governance structures is critical in realizing SDG 6. These studies reinforce the understanding that achieving universal and equitable access to water and sanitation is not solely a technical or financial challenge, but fundamentally a governance issue.

Lockwood and Smits (2011) study introduced the service delivery approach (SDA) to rural water supply in developing countries, emphasizing governance over infrastructure inputs. It highlighted that strong governance defined through clear institutional roles, long-term financing, monitoring, and accountability is essential to ensuring continuous WASH services delivery. The authors found that countries like Ghana and Uganda that adopted a governance-oriented SDA model showed better long-term functionality of WASH services and higher customers satisfaction. And Singh et al. (2022) underscores that achieving SDG 6 depends as much on governance, finance and institutions as on technologies

adding that institutional challenges are recurrent barriers

World Bank (2017) found that good governance mechanisms including inclusive policymaking, participatory planning, and reliable regulation were strongly associated with improved WASH access among marginalized populations. It cited Ethiopia's One WASH National Programme (OWNP) and Kenya's Water Act of 2016 as critical governance reforms that enhanced service delivery equity. The report links inclusive WASH governance to targets 6.2 (access to sanitation and hygiene) and 6.3 (improving water quality and wastewater treatment), showing that governance can close access gaps.

Jiménez et al. (2020) presents a conceptual framework that links governance dimensions such as legal frameworks, decentralization, financing, and information systems to community participation in WASH planning and monitoring. Using case studies from Burkina Faso, Mozambique, and Uganda, the study found that inclusive governance environments facilitated more equitable and effective service delivery. The study provides evidence on SDG 6.b, emphasizing that governance fosters local engagement, which improves service relevance and sustainability. UN-Water (2020) drawing data from over 100 countries, showed that nations with well-coordinated WASH governance frameworks especially those with clear institutional mandates, robust national policies, and systematic data reporting had stronger trajectories toward achieving SDG 6. In Sub-Saharan Africa, Rwanda and Senegal were highlighted for their policy alignment and intersectoral coordination, which led to significant improvements in WASH service coverage. This study illustrates how governance attributes such as leadership, planning, and monitoring are direct enablers for the delivering of WASH services.

Onda et al. (2022) explored governance-related barriers to WASH services across African countries. It concluded that policy fragmentation, low political will, lack of decentralization, and weak regulatory institutions were primary obstacles to achieving SDG 6. However, it also presented evidence that countries with reforms focused on governance such as decentralization in Mali and regulatory strengthening in Tanzania reported improved WASH functionality and service continuity. The review explicitly connects governance enablers to outcomes in water access, quality, and management.

Trémolet et al. (2018), in this study evaluated how basic governance principles like transparency, accountability, coordination, and participation impact WASH outcomes. Using case studies from Zambia, Sierra Leone, and Nigeria, it found that where communities were engaged in budgeting and monitoring, service delivery improved, and failure were reduced. The study demonstrates how building governance capacity strengthens efforts toward universal access and promotes resilient WASH systems aligned with SDG 6.1 and 6.2. Numerous countries in SSA have adopted governance-oriented approaches to improve WASH service delivery with varying degrees of success. For instance, Rwanda, through its decentralized governance system, has integrated WASH planning and budgeting into district-level development strategies. The country's National Strategy for Transformation (NST1) and District Development Strategies have mainstreamed WASH indicators, which has led to measurable improvements in access to safe water (currently above 87%) and basic sanitation in both rural and urban areas (WHO/UNICEF, 2022). Strong political commitment, performance-based financing, and community ownership have been key success factors. Ethiopia implemented the One WASH National Programme (OWNP), a government-led, multi-sectoral approach that harmonizes the efforts of water, health, education, and finance ministries. By establishing clear institutional roles, joint planning mechanisms, and a consolidated funding framework, Ethiopia improved WASH access in rural areas from 35% in 2010 to over 60% by 2020 (World Bank, 2021). Uganda's Good Governance in WASH (GG-WASH) framework emphasizes citizen engagement, transparency, and anti-corruption initiatives. The use of performance contracts and public expenditure tracking surveys

has improved service accountability at the local level, particularly in water user committees (GIZ, 2020). In Senegal, the delegated management model for urban water supply, involving private sector participation under public regulation, improved efficiency and cost recovery while expanding access to underserved areas (World Bank, 2018). South Africa, leveraging its constitutional recognition of access to water as a basic human right, has established a strong legislative framework including the Water Services Act (1997) and the National Water Act (1998) that mandates municipalities to deliver equitable services. Despite persistent inequalities, these laws have laid a governance foundation for improving rural access and advancing SDG 6 targets.

While these examples demonstrate that effective WASH governance can catalyze progress toward SDG 6, many countries in the region still grapple with fragmented institutional mandates, overlapping jurisdictions, inadequate financing, poor regulatory oversight, and weak monitoring and evaluation systems. In some contexts, political interference, corruption, and lack of community ownership have further undermined governance effectiveness.

The cumulative evidence from scholarly literature, government reports, and international assessment underscores the critical role that effective WASH governance plays in achieving SDG 6. Countries that have invested in coherent policy frameworks, decentralized implementation, participatory mechanisms, and regulatory oversight have recorded notable progress in WASH service delivery (Jimenez et al. 2021, World bank 2021). As this systematic review will further explore, the linkage between governance and SDG 6 is not merely theoretical but demonstrate through real world intervention offering valuable lessons for lagging context in Sub-Saharan Africa. Table 1 below shows graphical presentation of the studies from Jimenez et all (2021), World bank (2021), around policies, institutions and regulations (PIRs) as quoted above.

Table 1: Governance-oriented approaches to improve WASH service delivery

S/n	Country	Governance reform	Outcome	SDG 6 link
1	Rwanda	Decentralized Planning and Performance-based financing	Increased access to basic water (87%) and Sanitation Services	6.1, 6.2
2	Ethiopia	One WASH National Programme	Improved WASH access through multi-sectoral coordination	6.1, 6.2
3	Senegal	Delegated Management of Urban Water	Expanded access and improved cost recovery	6.1, 6. a
4	Uganda	Good Governance in WASH (GG-WASH)	Improved community oversight and functionality of water systems	6.b
5	South Africa	Right-based legislative Framework	Institutional accountability for service provision	6.1, 6.2

This study adopts a systematic review approach to synthesize the evidence on governance-related barriers to WASH service delivery in Sub-Saharan Africa. It explores how governance systems or the lack of governance systems and enabling environment either facilitate or hinder progress toward SDG 6. In doing so, it draws lessons from countries with innovative and integrated governance approaches, critically examines institutional arrangements and policy frameworks, and identifies gaps in knowledge and practice. The review contributes to a deeper understanding of how to design context-sensitive, inclusive, and resilient governance mechanisms capable of closing the WASH access gap in Sub-Saharan Africa by 2030 and beyond. Therefore, the objectives of this study are to identify key policies, institutions and regulations (PIR)-related barriers hindering WASH service delivery, to synthesize empirical evidence from studies across various countries, and to explore how strengthened governance and institutional frameworks have improved WASH outcomes.

2.0. Methodology

This study utilized a systematic literature review to synthesize peer reviewed evidence on Governance Barriers on WASH Service Delivery in Sub-Sahara Africa, conducted in line with the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta Analyses (PRISMA) 2020 guidelines (Figure 1). PRISMA guidelines provided structured, transparent, reproducible, policy relevant and standardized framework for reporting the synthesized peer review, thereby minimizes bias, improves quality and credibility and as well facilitates comparability through visual clarity. These aligns to the primary purpose of the systematic review aimed at building a robust evidence base to inform and strengthen WASH governance through the development of effective PIRs and efficient implementation/improvement of WASH services delivery across SSAs. Exclusively the key governance barriers to WASH services delivery were prioritized.

2.1. Identification

A Peer-reviewed literature was retrieved from academic databases including Secondary data, Web of Science, PubMed, and Google Scholar. A total of 1,218 were originally identified in the category of Google Scholar (1,108), PubMed (53), Web of Science (45), Secondary data (12). Search terms combined keywords related to governance and WASH, such as “sanitation governance,” “water governance,” “policy,” “institutions,” “regulation,” “Sub-Saharan Africa.” Boolean operators (AND/OR) were applied to refine results. Searches were limited to publications between 2010 and 2024 to ensure relevance to the SDG era.

Secondary data also included high-quality reports from reputable organizations such as the World Bank, WHO/UNICEF Joint Monitoring Programme, AMCOW, AfDB, and Transparency International. Although these do not undergo peer-review, they provided empirical evidence on governance structures and sector performance in contexts where peer-reviewed studies were scarce. Care was taken to limit reliance on grey literature and prioritize peer-reviewed sources where available, thus on the overall, out of 38 reviewed texts, only 12 were grey literature.

2.2. Eligibility Criteria

Eligibility criteria were structured using the PICOS framework. Studies were included if they focused on populations affected by WASH service delivery in the rural, peri urban, and urban areas in Sub-Saharan Africa, examined Policies, Institutional arrangement, governance-related interventions and/or service delivery mechanisms aimed at improving WASH service delivery, reported outcomes related to barriers or facilitators of achieving SDG 6, and were based on empirical designs including qualitative, quantitative, mixed methods, or systematic reviews. Both peer-reviewed and high-quality grey literature published between 2000–2025 were considered.

Figure 1 Shows a diagrammatic representation of the PRISMA Flow Diagram of the methodology

The methodological quality of included studies was assessed using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT, 2018) which allows for the appraisal of qualitative and quantitative (randomized, non-randomized, descriptive) and mixed methods studies. Each study was independently evaluated by two reviewers, and discrepancies were resolved through consensus. Quality ratings were reported narratively and used to assess the robustness of synthesized evidence.

2.3. Inclusion Criteria

Studies were included if they focused on populations in the rural, semi urban and urban areas in Sub-Saharan Africa (P), investigated governance-related barriers relating to policies, institutional, financial, and political environmental issues or interventions influencing WASH service delivery (I), Studies comparing different governance models, interventions, institutional arrangements across countries with or without comparators (C), and reported outcomes on barriers, facilitators, or progress towards SDG 6 targets (O). Eligible designs included qualitative, quantitative, mixed-methods studies, systematic reviews, and credible policy analyses (S). Only studies published between 2000 and 2025 in English were considered to maintain relevance of the review to the SDGs. Studies were further assessed using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT, 2018) to ensure methodological rigor.

2.4. Exclusion Criteria

Studies were excluded based on predefined criteria to maintain focus and methodological rigor, mostly if they were not conducted in Sub-Saharan Africa or did not disaggregate Sub-Sahara Africa countries or reflective of SSA data. The review was geographically bounded, thus pooled global studies without SSA specific data cannot inform SSA

governance thus were excluded. Studies that are not focused on WASH service delivery or governance-related barriers such as policy, institutional arrangement, Regulations, financing were all excluded from the peer review. Studies that were non-empirical (editorials, commentaries) or conference abstracts without sufficient methods/results for appraisal or that used ineligible designs (e.g., modelling without empirical validation) as specified in the protocol were also excluded; In same vein, all studies that were published outside the period 2000–2025 or in languages not eligible for translation (English language) were excluded. The studies that lacked sufficient methodological detail to permit appraisal using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT) after attempts to contact authors were also excluded. After applying these criteria, 40 studies were shortlisted for full text review. Reasons for exclusion at full-text review will be recorded and tabulated with counts and examples in the PRISMA flow diagram and supplementary materials.

2.5. Study Design and Framework

This review adopted a systematic review design, to identify, assess and synthesize the governance barriers of WASH Service Delivery in Sub Saharan Africa. Systematic reviews are extensively recognized as a rigorous method for synthesizing evidence on a defined research question using transparent and reproducible processes. Systematic reviews differ from narrative reviews because they apply explicit eligibility criteria, structured search strategies, and critical appraisal of included studies to minimize bias and enhance reliability (Moher et al., 2009; Higgins et al., 2022).

The study followed the Preferred Reporting Items for Systematic Reviews and Meta-Analyses (PRISMA 2020) guidelines, which provide a structured framework for planning, conducting, and reporting systematic reviews (Page et al., 2021). PRISMA was chosen because it ensures transparency in article selection, enhances reproducibility, and supports the credibility of synthesized findings, well suited for policy recommendation

Two complementary analytical frameworks were applied to structure the eligibility criteria and quality appraisal of studies; PICOS Framework (Population, Intervention/Exposure, Comparator, Outcomes, Study Design) and Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT, 2018 version).

PICOS was used to define the inclusion and exclusion criteria for the review. This framework is widely recommended in systematic reviews as it helps to systematically structure research questions and ensure that only relevant studies are included (Methley et al., 2014).

In this study, the Population was people and institutions in Sub-Saharan Africa, the Intervention/Exposure was governance(PIRs) and institutional arrangements in WASH, the Comparator was either absent or implicit (weak vs. strong governance settings), the Outcomes were barriers and facilitators of WASH service delivery in relation to SDG 6, and the Study Design covered qualitative, quantitative, and mixed-methods evidence.

The MMAT was applied to appraise the methodological quality of included studies. This tool was deployed because of its suitability for systematic reviews like this one, where evidence spans qualitative, quantitative, and mixed-methods research (Hong et al., 2018). The MMAT allowed consistent evaluation across multiple study designs without privileging one type of evidence over another. Each included study was screened using the initial two questions of the MMAT, followed by design-specific criteria to assess methodological robustness.

In summary, the work used a systematic review design to ascertain the governance barrier to WASH service delivery, guided by the PRISMA 2020 statement to ensure transparency and reproducibility (Page et al., 2021). The PICOS framework was applied to structure the eligibility criteria and guide study selection (Methley et al., 2014). Finally, the MMAT (2018) was employed to appraise methodological quality across included qualitative, quantitative, and mixed-

methods studies (Hong et al., 2018).

2.6. Search Strategy and Data Sources

A comprehensive search strategy was developed in line with PRISMA 2020 guidelines (Page et al., 2021) to identify peer-reviewed and grey literature on barriers to WASH service delivery in Sub-Saharan Africa. The search covered publications between January 2000 and September 2025 to capture evidence from the MDG and SDG eras.

Electronic databases searched included PubMed/MEDLINE, Web of Science, and google Scholar, supplemented by ProQuest Dissertations & Theses Global. To ensure wider coverage, grey literature was retrieved from the WHO/UNICEF Joint Monitoring Programme (JMP), World Bank, African Development Bank, WaterAid, IRC WASH, SWA Partnership, and relevant government ministry websites. Additionally, Google Scholar was searched (first 1,108 results) to capture non-indexed studies, Reference lists of all included studies and key reviews were also hand-searched to identify additional eligible publications.

The search strategy combined controlled vocabulary (MeSH terms) and free-text keywords across three domains: (i) WASH services (e.g., “water supply,” “sanitation,” “hygiene,” “WASH governance”), (ii) barriers (e.g., “challenges,” “constraints,” “obstacles,” “determinants”), and (iii) geographical scope (e.g., “Sub-Saharan Africa” and country-specific names). Boolean operators (AND/OR) were applied to refine searches. All retrieved records were imported into EndNote/Zotero for management, with duplicates removed. Titles were screened including, abstracts, and full texts against predefined PICOS eligibility criteria, and methodological quality was appraised using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT, 2018).

2.7. Screening and Selection Process

All identified records were imported into EndNote/Zotero and duplicates removed. Screening followed the PRISMA 2020 guidelines (Page et al., 2021). The process was conducted in three stages: (i) titles were screened to exclude irrelevant studies, (ii) abstracts were assessed against predefined PICOS eligibility criteria, and (iii) full texts of potentially eligible studies were reviewed in detail. The initial search yielded 1,218 records, of which 645 duplicates were removed, leaving 573 unique studies. Titles and abstracts of these studies were screened for relevance to review objectives, after which 350 studies were retained for full text assessment. Following a detailed eligibility review, 223 studies were excluded due to methodological limitations or lack of direct relevance. Ultimately, 40 studies met all inclusion criteria and were synthesized in the final review

Reasons for exclusion at the full-text stage were documented. The overall process was summarized in a PRISMA 2020 flow diagram below, showing the number of records retrieved, screened, excluded, and finally included in the review.

2.8. Data Extraction and Synthesis

A standardized data extraction form was developed to ensure consistency and accuracy across all included studies. Extracted information covered: (i) bibliographic details (author, year, country), (ii) study design and methodology, (iii) population and setting, (iv) type of WASH service examined, (v) identified barriers to service delivery, and (vi) key outcomes and policy implications. Data were independently extracted by two reviewers, with discrepancies resolved through discussion.

Given the heterogeneity of study designs and outcomes, a narrative synthesis approach was adopted rather than meta-analysis. Findings were thematically organized around governance, institutional, financial, infrastructural, socio-

cultural, environmental, and political barriers to WASH service delivery. Themes were compared across sub-Saharan Africa countries and study types to identify recurrent patterns, context-specific variations, and gaps in evidence.

Where applicable, the synthesis highlighted the linkages between WASH governance and the attainment of SDG 6, drawing on examples of effective institutional arrangements and policy frameworks from Sub-Saharan African countries. The Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT, 2018) was applied to assess the methodological quality of included studies, ensuring that the synthesis reflected the strength and reliability of the available evidence.

2.9. Quality Appraisal

The methodological quality of all included studies was assessed using the Mixed Methods Appraisal Tool (MMAT, 2018 version) (Hong et al., 2018). This tool was selected because it allows the appraisal of qualitative, quantitative, and mixed-methods studies within a single framework, making it particularly suitable for systematic reviews that include diverse study designs.

Each study was first screened with two general MMAT questions on the clarity of research questions and appropriateness of data collection methods. Subsequently, design-specific criteria were applied, covering five domains: (i) qualitative research, (ii) randomized controlled trials, (iii) non-randomized quantitative studies, (iv) quantitative descriptive studies, and (v) mixed-methods studies.

Each study was rated on:

- *Relevance and clarity of the research question*
- *Appropriateness of methodology and sampling*
- *Transparency in data collection and analysis*
- *Credibility of findings and ethical considerations*

A speculative appraisal was conducted to resolve discrepancies. The results of the appraisal were not used to exclude studies but to inform the interpretation and weighting of evidence during synthesis. Studies rated as higher quality were given greater emphasis in drawing conclusions, while lower-quality studies were used cautiously to identify potential gaps and areas for further research.

3.0 Results

The synthesis of 40 studies on WASH governance in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) revealed five recurring domains of barriers: policy incoherence, institutional fragmentation, weak regulation, financing constraints, and limited participation. The integration of findings across studies shows that while the specific contexts vary, governance challenges consistently shape the performance and sustainability of WASH services in SSA.

Policy Incoherence and Misalignment- Across 25 studies, policy incoherence emerged as a major barrier. Several countries operate with overlapping or outdated policy documents, creating duplication and confusion. In Nigeria, for example, conflicting mandates between the National Water Resources Policy (2016) and the National Sanitation Policy (2005) were linked to fragmented service delivery (Akpabio et al., 2020). Similar findings were reported in Ghana, where rural water strategies lacked clear links to sanitation and hygiene objectives (Moriarty et al., 2013). Multi-country reviews confirmed that the absence of harmonized WASH policies limits coordinated action and slows progress toward SDG 6 (Jiménez et al., 2021; Yasmin et al., 2023). However, evidence from Rwanda and Ethiopia suggests that countries with coherent, integrated policy frameworks show stronger progress in extending services (World Bank, 2021; AfDB, 2021).

Institutional Fragmentation and Weak Capacity- Twenty two studies identified institutional fragmentation and weak local capacity as persistent governance challenges. Findings from Kenya and Uganda highlighted overlapping responsibilities among multiple agencies, which created accountability gaps and duplication of efforts (WASREB, 2020; Tumwebaze & Mosler, 2014). South Africa provided an example where strong constitutional rights did not translate into effective services because of under-resourced municipalities (Koelble & Siddle, 2014; Zwane & Maleka, 2020). Evidence from Ethiopia and Senegal, however, showed that strong inter-ministerial coordination platforms improved vertical alignment between national and subnational authorities, leading to better service coverage (World Bank, 2018; Evaristo et al., 2023).

Weak Regulatory Oversight- Eight studies highlighted weak or absent regulatory systems as key obstacles. In Zambia, rural water systems remained largely unregulated, undermining equity and sustainability (NWASCO, 2021). Studies across SSA found that regulatory capture by political elites and weak enforcement of standards contributed to service failures (Transparency International, 2020). Conversely, where regulators had strong authority and autonomy—as in Senegal's delegated management model—WASH service performance was significantly improved (World Bank, 2017;).

Financing Constraints and Accountability Gaps- Thirteen studies documented financing as both a technical and governance challenge. Donor dependency was widespread, with many WASH projects collapsing when external funding ended (Bain et al., 2014; Nyarko et al., 2021). In addition, mismanagement of funds and corruption reduced trust in sector institutions (Transparency International, 2020). Yet, innovative financing approaches such as Rwanda's performance-based contracts and Uganda's public expenditure tracking mechanisms demonstrated how governance reforms in financial management can enhance sustainability (GIZ, 2020; AfDB, 2021). Importantly, this review found that financing sustainability depends less on absolute resource availability and more on governance structures that ensure efficiency, transparency, and accountability.

Limited and Tokenistic Community Participation - Seven studies emphasized that community engagement is often symbolic rather than substantive. Evidence from Malawi and Kenya showed that community management models were prone to failure when not backed by institutional support (Chowns, 2015; Hope, 2015). Reviews of informal settlements in SSA and Asia also revealed that participation is often limited to consultation without decision-making authority (Sinharoy et al., 2019; Nguyen et al., 2020). However, empirical evidence from Ethiopia's One WASH Programme and Senegal's delegated management model demonstrated that structured participation—where communities are empowered in planning, monitoring, and accountability—leads to more sustainable WASH outcomes (World Bank, 2021; Onda et al., 2022).

3.1.Synthesis of Findings

Taken together, the 40 studies converge on the finding that governance—not technology or finance alone—determines the sustainability and equity of WASH services in SSA. Policy coherence, institutional coordination, regulatory enforcement, financing accountability, and genuine citizen participation consistently emerged as decisive factors. Countries that combined these governance elements, such as Rwanda, Ethiopia, and Senegal, demonstrated stronger progress toward SDG 6, while those with fragmented governance systems lagged despite donor investments (Table 2).

Table 2: Tabular Representation of synthesis of Literature and Empirical Evidence

S/N	Study (Author, Year)	Country / Scope	Focus	Key finding (literature / empirical evidence)
1	Akpabio et al. (2020)	Nigeria	Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documents fragmented national WASH policies - This is a big disconnect between policy design and community realities, undermining implementation.
2	Bain et al. (2014)	Multi-country/global (Ethiopia, Nigeria, Ghana, Kenya, Uganda, Malawi, Tanzania and South Africa)	Institutions/Health exposure	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Systematic review evidencing widespread faecal contamination exposure - highlights health burden and governance gaps in monitoring.
3	Koelble & Siddle (2014)	South Africa	Institutions/Policy	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shows that decentralization reforms have uneven implementation - municipal capacity constraints limit service delivery.
4	Moriarty et al. (2013)	Ghana/ global practice	Policy/Institution	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Argues for a service-delivery approach; finds unclear local authority roles hinder equitable rural coverage. - Poorly defined institutional roles, lacking clarity, adding also that policies are often in place although they lack implementation
5	NWASCO (2021)	Zambia	Regulations	Reports urban-focused regulation leaving rural schemes unregulated and underperforming.
6	Tumwebaze & Mosler (2014)	Uganda	Community/Behavior	Empirical study on toilet cleaning behavior showing social and contextual drivers of hygiene uptake.
7	WASREB (2020)	Kenya	Institution / Performance	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Documents multiple agencies - Overlapping mandates creating accountability gaps in water services.
8	World Bank (2018)	Ethiopia	Institutions/Program	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Evaluates One WASH National Programme: - - finds improved coordination where vertical integration is strong.
9	WHO & UNICEF JMP (2021)	Multi-country (Burundi, Ethiopia, Kenya, Malawi, Rwanda, Tanzania, Uganda and Zambia)	Regulation / Monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Shows many countries lack enforcement for rural water quality and hygiene standards. - Inconsistency in policy leading to non-adherence
10	AMCOW (2019)	Sub-Saharan Africa	Policy / Regional monitoring	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Regional synthesis identifying common policy and financing weaknesses across member states.
11	AfDB (2021)	Rwanda	Policy / Financing	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Country overview linking governance reforms to improved WASH indicators and financing gaps reduced by policy alignment.
12	Kanyangarara et al. (2021)	SSA health facilities (Ethiopia, Kenya, Liberia, Malawi, Senegal and Uganda)	Institutions / WASH in health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Health facility surveys indicate persistent WASH gaps, affecting infection control. - Reinforces health-facility governance gaps important for infection prevention.
13	Bayu et al. (2020)	Multi-country(Zambia, Namibia, Benin, Gabon)	SSA Policy / Equity	Highlights governance drivers of inequality in sanitation access across SSA to include Policy and Accountability, Regulations and Legislation
14	Sinharoy et al. (2019)	LMICs (incl. SSA-Kenya, South Africa)	Policy / Informal settlements	Reviews drivers/barriers for informal settlements; governance and planning shortfalls are primary constraints.

15	UNDP (2021)	Global (Liberia, Lebanon, Burundi, Libya, Mali, Sierra Leone, South Sudan, Somalia)	Governance / Accountability	Policy guidance showing accountability mechanisms improve sector performance.
16	Jiménez et al. (2021)	Multi-country / SWA cases (Sierra Leone, Senegal, Uganda, Pakistan, Madagascar)	Policy / Targets	Examines national WASH targets via governance lens; finds governance alignment critical for target attainment.
17	Yasmin et al. (2023)	Systematic review Kenya, (Uganda, Ethiopia, South Sudan)	Systems / Governance	Systematic review showing systems-level governance (coordination, capacity) influences WASH resilience.
18	Valcourt et al. (2020)	Kenya, Uganda, Ethiopia, and Ghana among others	Systems / Institutional	Finds system approaches reveal fragmentation and unclear roles as threats to sustainability.
19	Momberg et al. (2021)	SSA (child nutrition links) (South Africa, Uganda, Malawi, Ethiopia, Kenya)	Institutions / Outcomes	Links governance factors to WASH outcomes and child undernutrition, underscoring governance as mediator.
20	Page et al. (2021)	PRISMA guidance	Methods	PRISMA 2020 informs review reporting and justification for included studies.
21	Trémolet et al. (2018)	Multi-case analysis SSA countries include: Benin, Burkinafaso, Burundi, Ethiopia, Ghana, Ivory Coast, Kenya, Lesotho, Liberia, Madagascar, Mali, Morocco, Mozambique, Nigeria, Rwanda, Senegal, South Africa, Tanzania, Uganda, Zambia, Zimbabwe	Policy / Governance	Demonstrates that transparency, accountability and participation improve WASH outcomes in case countries.
22	Onda et al. (2022)	Comparative SSA (Zimbabwe, Ethiopia, Zambia, Kenya, Ghana, Tanzania, Uganda and Malawi	Governance barriers	Comparative analysis identifying policy fragmentation, low political will and weak regulatory institutions.
23	GIZ (2020)	Uganda	Governance Practice	Describes GG-WASH experiences: public expenditure tracking and performance contracts improve accountability.
24	World Bank (2017)	Multi-country/reforms (Angola, Benin, Burkina faso, Burundi, Cape Verde, Cameroon, Central African Republic, Chad, Comoros, Congo, Dem Rep, Cote d ivoire, Eritrea, Ethiopia, Gabon, Gambia, Ghana, Guinea-Bissau, Kenya, Lesotho, Liberia, Madagascar, Malawi, Mali, Mauritania, Mozambique, Nigeri, Nigeria, Rwanda, Sao tome and principe, Senegal, Sierra Leone, South Sudan, Tanzania,	Regulation / Institutional	Documents evidence that inclusive policymaking and reliable regulation improve access among marginalized groups. The 38 countries were scored on policy and institutional performance-including aspects of regulation, governance and service delivery capacity-
25	World Bank (2021)	Ethiopia	Program evaluation	Documents One WASH implementation progress and highlights remaining vertical coordination gaps.

26	Chowns (2015)	Malawi	Community management evaluation	Critical assessment showing community management has mixed efficiency and equity outcomes without institutional support.
27	Hope (2015)	Kenya	Community management	Empirical evidence that choice of community water management models affects sustainability and equity.
28	Koehler et al. (2015)	Rural Africa (Kenya and Uganda)	Financing mechanisms	Evaluates pump-priming payments and finds payment design tied to governance arrangements affects sustainability.
29	Smits & Lockwood (2013)	Financing review (Benin, Burkina Faso, Colombia, Ethiopia, Ghana, Honduras, Mozambique, south Africa, Uganda)	Financing / Policy	Argues financing models must be matched to governance capacity to be effective.
29	UNECA (2020)	Africa (Burkina Faso, Cote d' Ivoire, Kenya, Senegal, Uganda)	Financing policy	Outlines continental financing options; emphasizes domestic resource mobilization and governance reforms.
30	Van den Berg & Danilenko (2017)	Utilities performance (Burkina Faso, Kenya, Senegal, Uganda)	Institutional / Utility	The analysis of Uganda National Water and Sewerage Corporation (NWSC), Nairobi City Water and Sewerage Company(NCWSC), Societe de distribution d eau la cote d ivoire (SODECI), and Office National de l eau et de l assainissement (ONEA) of Burkina Faso shows that utility performance is determined by its regulatory and institutional factors
31	Wulich & Brewis (2014)	Cross-disciplinary (Democratic republic of congo, Ethiopia, Ghana, Kenya, Malawi, Nigeria, Uganda)	Social / Scarcity	Anthropological perspective showing resource insecurity interacts with governance to affect access.
32	Parker et al. (2016)	SSA (MHM) (Ghana, Kenya, Uganda)	Policy / Gender	Menstrual hygiene management governance challenges; policy gaps limit institutional responses.
33	Kanyangarara et al. (2021)	Health facilities SSA (Burkina Faso, Kenya, Malawi, Mauritania, Mozambique, Niger, Senegal, Sierra leone, Somalia, Tanzania, Uganda, Zimbabwe)	WASH in health	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> - Reinforces health-facility governance gaps important for infection prevention. - Adds that many countries lacked clear, enforceable national standards for WASH in Health facilities - Even when standards exist, there was limited compliance and enforcement due to weak institutional capacity - Fragmented institutional responsibility and overlaps were also identified.
34	Zwane & Maleka (2020)	South Africa (Limpopo)	Decentralization / Equity	Case study showing decentralized governance can both help and hinder equity depending on local capacity.
35	AMCOW (2022)	Africa regional (Kenya, Nigeria, Ethiopia, Cameroun, Burkina Faso, Sudan, Sierra Leone, Liberia, Tanzania, Zimbabwe, Mozambique)	Policy guidance	Regional sanitation guidelines emphasizing governance reforms; supports policy calls in this review.
36	Transparency International (2020)	Multi-country(Malawi, Rwanda, Senegal, Ghana, Botswana, Cape Verde, Chad, Eritrea, Comoros, Guinea Bissau, Democratic Republic of Congo, Equitoria Guinea, Sudan, South Sudan, Somalia)	Governance / Corruption	Empirical documentation of corruption impacts on water sector investments and service delivery.

4.0 Discussion

This systematic review provides evidence that the central constraints to WASH service delivery in Sub-Saharan Africa (SSA) are rooted not only in technical and financial challenges, but fundamentally in governance systems. By synthesizing 40 studies across 23 SSA countries, the review highlights recurring governance barriers: policy incoherence, institutional fragmentation, weak regulatory enforcement, inadequate financing, corruption, and limited community participation. These findings reinforce but also extend earlier arguments that governance is the “missing link” in achieving universal WASH access (Trémolet et al., 2018; Valcourt et al., 2020; Yasmin et al., 2023).

Policy incoherence emerged as a recurring barrier. Several studies revealed how outdated or overlapping policies undermine effective implementation. For example, in Nigeria, conflicting mandates between the National Water Resources Policy (2016) and the Sanitation Policy (2005) contribute to fragmented service delivery (Akpabio et al., 2020). Similar misalignments were reported in Ghana (Moriarty et al., 2013) and across multiple SSA countries where sectoral silos limit the integration of water, sanitation, and hygiene policies (Bayu et al., 2020; Jiménez et al., 2021). This review contributes new knowledge by consolidating evidence that harmonized national WASH policies, when coupled with clear roles for subnational governments, lead to better outcomes—as demonstrated by Rwanda's decentralized planning and Ethiopia's One WASH National Programme (World Bank, 2021; WHO/UNICEF, 2022).

Institutional fragmentation and capacity deficits were also strongly emphasized across the reviewed literature. Case studies from Kenya and Uganda illustrate how overlapping mandates among agencies create accountability gaps and duplication (WASREB, 2020; Tumwebaze & Mosler, 2014). Similar challenges were documented in South Africa, where despite strong constitutional rights, corruption and weak local capacity continue to constrain service delivery (Koelble & Siddle, 2014; Zwane & Maleka, 2020). Yet, this study adds to knowledge by showing that cross-sectoral teams and inter-ministerial committees—when properly resourced—enhance vertical coordination and improve equity, as evidenced in Ethiopia and Senegal (World Bank, 2018; Evaristo et al., 2023).

Weak regulatory oversight was another persistent barrier. In Zambia, rural water systems remain largely unregulated, leading to inequities in service provision (NWASCO, 2021). Regulatory capture by politically connected providers was also reported across several countries (Transparency International, 2020). However, where regulators were empowered, such as in Senegal's delegated management model, accountability and service continuity improved significantly (World Bank, 2017;). The cumulative evidence underscores that regulatory strength—not just the presence of policies determines whether service delivery frameworks achieve their intended outcomes.

Financing and accountability challenges cut across nearly all studies. Over-reliance on donor funding was shown to create unsustainable models, with many projects collapsing once external funding ended (Bain et al., 2014; Nyarko et al., 2021). At the same time, corruption and mismanagement reduced institutional credibility (Transparency International, 2020). Yet, innovations in financing, such as Rwanda's performance-based mechanisms and Uganda's public expenditure tracking surveys, demonstrate how governance reforms can improve both sustainability and trust (GIZ, 2020; African Development Bank, 2021). This review expands knowledge by linking financing sustainability directly to governance practices, rather than framing it solely as an economic challenge.

Community participation was often symbolic, with citizens excluded from meaningful decision-making (Nguyen et al., 2020; Sinharoy et al., 2019). However, the review highlights examples where structured participation improved outcomes. Ethiopia's One WASH Programme institutionalized community roles in planning and monitoring, while Senegal's delegated management model empowered local users (World Bank, 2021; Onda et al., 2022). These cases

illustrate that participation, when embedded in governance frameworks, contributes not just to ownership but to long-term service sustainability.

Synthesis of the 40 studies generates two new insights. First, WASH outcomes in SSA are not primarily determined by technology or finance, but by governance arrangements that enable or constrain how resources are mobilized, policies are implemented, and services are delivered. Second, governance reforms that integrate coherence, accountability, and citizen participation consistently show stronger progress toward SDG 6 than infrastructure-focused interventions alone (Momberg et al., 2021; Singh et al., 2022; Yasmin et al., 2023).

This review therefore contributes to knowledge by reframing WASH challenges in SSA as fundamentally governance driven. While previous literature recognized governance as important, this synthesis demonstrates across multiple countries and contexts that effective governance is the decisive factor in achieving equitable, sustainable, and resilient WASH services.

5.0. Summary of findings

The systematic review identified several governance barriers to WASH service delivery in SSA. Institutional Fragmentation, overlapping mandates and poor coordination across ministries often lead to duplication of efforts and inefficiencies (Trémolet, 2019). Weak Policy Implementation is also a major barrier to weak WASH service delivery, while many SSA countries have adopted progressive WASH policies, enforcement and implementation remain limited due to lack of capacity and political will (Mihayo & Mkama, 2021). Financing Constraints, often inadequate domestic financing and reliance on donor funds limit the sustainability of WASH programs (Nyarko et al., 2021). Corruption and Accountability Gaps through Mismanagement of funds and lack of transparency undermine trust and service delivery (Transparency International, 2020). Community Participation Deficits, engagement of local communities is often symbolic rather than substantive, reducing ownership and sustainability of WASH projects (Nguyen et al., 2020) and finally Political Interference driven by Short-term political interests often override long-term service delivery goals, particularly in election cycles (Adejumo & Adepoju, 2022).

6.0. Limitations of Study

Limited Geographic Representation-While the review included studies from several Sub-Saharan African countries (e.g., Nigeria, Ghana, Kenya, Uganda, Ethiopia, South Africa), not all countries in the region were equally represented due to the uneven availability of published research and data. In addition to limited geographic representation is language restrictions, only English-language literature was included. This may have excluded relevant studies published in French (e.g., from Francophone West Africa), Portuguese (e.g., Angola, Mozambique), or local languages, which may hold valuable insights. The review excluded non-governance-related barriers, such as socio-cultural taboos, technological/infrastructure limitation. While these are also critical, they were outside the defined scope which focused on Policies, institutions and regulations.

The review synthesized findings from existing literature without conducting primary fieldwork. This limits the ability to validate or update older findings, especially in rapidly changing governance or policy contexts. Additionally, most of the studies reviewed were from peer-reviewed journals and institutional reports, which may over-represent successful interventions or more accessible research sites. Unpublished failures or grey literature from rural or under-researched areas may have been missed. The literature search focused on studies published between 2010 and 2024. Earlier foundational work or very recent data (from 2025) may not have been included due to access limitations. Finally, different studies used varying definitions of WASH access, institutional performance, or regulatory strength, making

direct comparison across countries and studies more difficult.

7.0. Recommendation

This review identified governance-related barriers—policy incoherence, institutional fragmentation, weak regulatory oversight, inadequate financing, corruption, and limited community engagement—as the primary obstacles to WASH service delivery in Sub-Saharan Africa. Based on these findings, the following recommendations are proposed:

- I. Enhance Policy Coherence and Alignment:** Countries should harmonize overlapping and outdated WASH policies, such as Nigeria's dual National Water Resources Policy (2016) and Sanitation Policy (2005), to ensure unified frameworks that clearly assign responsibilities across ministries and tiers of government.
- II. Strengthen Institutional Capacity and Coordination:** Evidence from Kenya and Uganda shows that fragmented agencies and under-resourced local governments undermine service delivery. Strengthening vertical coordination between national and local authorities, coupled with adequate human and financial resources, is critical for effective implementation.
- III. Reform and Enforce Regulatory Frameworks:** Regulatory gaps, as seen in Zambia where rural water schemes remain unregulated, highlight the need for comprehensive regulatory coverage. Independent regulators should be empowered to enforce standards, protect consumer rights, and curb politically connected providers from operating without oversight.
- IV. Promote Accountability and Anti-Corruption Mechanisms:** Mismanagement of WASH funds and political interference remain significant governance risks. Transparent budgeting, public expenditure tracking (as piloted in Uganda's GG-WASH framework), and citizen scorecards can help reduce corruption and restore trust in institutions.
- V. Mobilize and Sustain Domestic Financing:** Over-reliance on donor-driven models creates unsustainable systems, as noted in several SSA contexts. Governments should prioritize domestic resource mobilization, performance-based financing (as in Rwanda), and integration of WASH into national budgetary frameworks to ensure long-term sustainability.
- VI. Institutionalize Genuine Community Participation:** Community involvement is often symbolic rather than substantive. Lessons from Ethiopia's One WASH Programme and Senegal's delegated management model show that when communities and local users are empowered in planning, budgeting, and monitoring, WASH outcomes are more sustainable and equitable.
- VII. Integrate WASH Governance into Broader Development and Climate Resilience Strategies:** Given the interdependence between water security, public health, and climate risks, WASH governance should be embedded within national development strategies and climate adaptation frameworks. This will ensure multi-sectoral synergies and resilience in service delivery.

Future research should include primary data collection across more diverse countries, incorporate multilingual sources, and consider integrating socio-cultural factors for a more holistic understanding of WASH service barriers.

8.0. Conclusion

This systematic review demonstrates that the most persistent barriers to WASH service delivery in Sub-Saharan Africa are not merely technical or financial but deeply rooted in governance systems—particularly in the areas of policy coherence, institutional capacity, and regulatory enforcement. The evidence across 40 reviewed studies shows that while infrastructure expansion and donor investments have improved access in some contexts, these gains remain fragile in the absence of enabling governance frameworks. Countries that have integrated WASH into broader national development strategies, established inclusive accountability mechanisms, and invested in decentralized but well-coordinated

institutions have made measurable progress toward SDG 6. Conversely, contexts where governance is fragmented, politically captured, or under-resourced continue to face inequities in service delivery, especially for rural communities, informal settlements, and marginalized groups. The knowledge generated from this review highlights that achieving universal access to safe water and sanitation by 2030 requires moving beyond infrastructure provision to strengthening the governance architecture that underpins WASH services. Specifically, three insights emerge. First, WASH must be recognized as both a governance and a rights issue, where policy alignment and institutional accountability directly determine equity of access. Second, financing sustainability is as much a governance question as an economic one—mobilizing domestic resources, curbing corruption, and institutionalizing transparent expenditure tracking are prerequisites for lasting progress. Third, community engagement must evolve from symbolic consultation to structured participation that empowers citizens to shape, monitor, and hold institutions accountable for WASH outcomes.

In conclusion, this study contributes to knowledge by consolidating the evidence that governance is the missing link in Sub-Saharan Africa's sanitation and water agenda. Strengthened governance systems—rooted in policy coherence, institutional clarity, accountability, and inclusive participation—are indispensable for breaking the cycle of donor dependency, inequity, and unsustainability. For policymakers, this means prioritizing governance reforms as a central strategy for accelerating SDG 6. For researchers, it underscores the need for more empirical, cross-country, and context-sensitive analyses of how governance arrangements translate into service outcomes. Ultimately, the pathway to universal WASH access in Africa lies not only in building more infrastructure, but in building stronger, more accountable, and more inclusive governance systems that can sustain services for generations to come.

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